

Study of Formation Constants of Substituted Salicylanils and 2'-Hydroxysalicylanils

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The proton-ligand stability constants of some substituted salicylanils and 2'-hydroxysalicylanils have been studied by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique in water-dioxane medium (1 : 3 v/v) at $\mu \sim 0.1$ (NaClO₄) and at 30° (± 0.1). The results have been discussed on the basis of the electromeric effects of substituent groups with regard to their nature and position in the salicylaldehyde and aniline nucleus.

The proton-ligand stability constants for closely related substituted anils are found to vary in the following order in terms of their substituents.

2'-CH₃ < 3'-CH₃ < 4'-CH₃ and similarly 2'-chloro < 3'-chloro < 4'-chloro and further as propiophenone < acetophenone.

SCHIFF bases derived from the condensation reaction of aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic and aromatic amines represent an important series of widely studied ligands¹⁻⁴. In the present investigation the authors have undertaken the study of formation constants of a series of fourteen closely related Schiff-base ligands obtained by the reaction of different aldehydes with a number of amines to explore the equilibria which exists when the metal ions interact with these ligands in solution.

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents used in the study were either A.R. grade or purified by conventional methods before use.

Preparation of chelating ligands: Salicylanils and 2'-hydroxysalicylanils were prepared by following the reported method⁵. Compound nos. 3 to 8 were prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde and corresponding amine, compound nos. 9 to 12 by condensing 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone with aniline and *o*-aminophenol, and compound nos. 13 and 14 by condensing resorcylddehyde and benzaldehyde with *o*-aminophenol. The compounds were recrystallised from methanol and preserved in vacuum desiccator. Their purity was ascertained by elemental analysis and checking their melting points.

Bjerrum-Calvin^{6,7} pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸ was followed to determine proton-ligand stability constants in dioxane-water (3 : 1, v/v) medium at constant temperature 30° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) and in presence of 0.8M sodium perchlorate to maintain constant ionic strength ($\mu \sim 0.1$).

Results and Discussion

The relation in dioxane-water medium was reported⁹ in mixtures of different compositions to follow the equation

$$-\log (H) = B + \log f + \log U^{\circ}H \quad (1)$$

where $U^{\circ}H$ is a correction factor. This correction factor for pH was used by Bjerrum in his "formation function" for \bar{n}_A which on simplification expressed as

$$\bar{n}_A = y - \frac{(V'' - V')}{(V'' + V')} \cdot \frac{(N + E^{\circ})}{C_2^{\circ}} \quad (2)$$

All the terms involved in the equation have their usual significance and y was taken unity.

Proton-ligand constants corresponding to acid dissociation: All the ligands studied in this investigation are involved in the formation of single complexes like LH. The formation function for such 1 : 1 complexes is given by the equation

$$\bar{n}_A + (\bar{n}_A - 1) pK_1^H / (\text{anti log } B) = 0 \quad (3)$$

This relation suggests that $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B should be linear. Such plots served to indicate the validity of $\bar{n}_A \sim B$ data and also useful to reject widely divergent data. However, the number of points that were rejected in all the cases was very small. Equation (3) may be written as

$$\log pK_1^H = B + \log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A) \quad (4)$$

The practical proton-ligand stability constants were calculated by using equation (4) and are summarised in Table 1. From the plot of $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B , the graphical values of $\log pK_1^H$ were obtained as intercepts on the X-axis and reported in Table 1. According to Bjerrum the half-integral values of the formation curves are

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Sl. no.	Ligand	Quantity calculated	log pK^H			Standard deviation
			Calcd.	Graphical	Half-integral	
1.	Salicylanil	OH d	10.45	10.45	10.46	0.202
2.	2'-Hydroxysalicylanil	OH d	9.99	10.05	10.05	0.249
3.	2'-Methylsalicylanil	OH d	10.32	10.35	10.35	—
4.	3'-Methylsalicylanil	OH d	10.38	10.40	10.40	0.200
5.	4'-Methylsalicylanil	OH d	10.76	10.80	10.80	0.225
6.	2'-Chlorosalicylanil	OH d	10.35	10.35	10.35	0.130
7.	3'-Chlorosalicylanil	OH d	10.37	10.39	10.39	0.159
8.	4'-Chlorosalicylanil	OH d	10.58	10.60	10.60	0.128
9.	2-Hydroxyacetophenoneanil	OH d	12.54	12.59	12.59	0.015
		N pa	3.18	3.16	3.15	—
10.	2'-Hydroxyacetophenone salicylanil	OH d	10.39	10.29	10.30	0.489
		N pa	3.20	3.39	3.20	0.519
11.	2-Hydroxypropiophenoneanil	OH d	12.31	12.36	12.36	0.026
		N pa	3.15	3.12	3.10	—
12.	2'-Hydroxypropiophenone salicylanil	OH d	9.98	9.98	9.98	0.232
		N pa	3.23	3.20	—	0.117
13.	4-Hydroxy-2'-hydroxysalicylanil	OH d	10.54	10.55	10.55	0.592
14.	2'-Hydroxyanil	OH d	11.42	11.50	11.45	0.369

d = dissociation ; pa = proton affinity.

equal to the formation constant, $\log pK^H$. Graphs obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A against B were wave like and the values of B at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ are equal to $\log pK_1^H$. The values of $\log pK_1^H$ thus obtained by half-integral method are reported in Table 1.

Since the absorption of proton was involved in the initial stages, equation (4) is modified as

$$\log pK_2^H = B + \log (\bar{n}_A - 1)/(2 - \bar{n}_A) \quad (5)$$

The proton affinity constant $\log pK_2^H$ of nitrogen were calculated using this equation. Plots of $\log (\bar{n}_A - 1)/(2 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B were linear and from the intercept on X-axis proton affinity constants were obtained. Half-integral value of B at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$ corresponds to proton-affinity constant of nitrogen. Such values were also obtained from proton-ligand formation curves ($\bar{n}_A \sim B$).

The values of proton-ligand stability constants calculated by the three methods reported (Table 1) reveal a close agreement. Standard deviation values calculated are also reported in Table 1. Values of $\log pK^H$ collected in the present investigation are obtained for the first time in dioxane-water (3 : 1 v/v) medium. Literature reveals that with the exception of salicylanil, work on stability constants of these ligands has not been undertaken so far. A $\log pK^H$ value of 10.44 was reported¹⁰ for salicylanil under identical experimental conditions. It was found that this value closely agrees with the value reported.

Examination of results in Table 1 shows that $\log pK^H$ values of all the substituted 2'-hydroxy salicylanils are lower than the corresponding substituted salicylanils. The increased acid strength of these compounds must be attributed to the presence of OH in aniline nucleus. The electro-negativity of nitrogen atom due to the presence of this substituent is apparently increasing, resulting in the formation of strong hydrogen bond with the

phenolic OH, which enhances the dissociation of OH. As a matter of fact-I effect of this substituent should cause a decrease in the electronic charge of nitrogen. However, the observed experimental results indicate contrary to this understanding. It is possible that in *ortho*-position + M effect of this substituent may be overcoming-I effect which might be resulting in the increased electronic charge on the nitrogen atom.

An examination of $\log pK^H$ values shows that a similar trend is noticed on *ortho*-substitution in aniline nucleus of the methyl- and chloro- groups and that the acidity of the ligands increases in the following order

Further glancing of $\log pK^H$ values indicates that for isomeric substituted ligands the difference in the magnitude of $\log pK^H$ though marginal is significant and that this difference can be assigned to the substituents present in the nucleus and their position in the molecule. Discussion on $\log pK^H$ values with smaller differences in a series holds good as they are beyond experimental errors. It was reported¹¹ that the standard test on $K < 3$ may be a failure in many cases of the data reported in the literature which does not necessarily mean that the complexes do not really exist or that their equilibrium constants are drastically different from the reported values. Similar is the case in the present investigation where all the general precautions^{12,13} in obtaining the most correct \bar{n}_A and $\log pK^H$ at each B value have been taken.

Introduction of methyl- and chloro- substituents at *meta*-position of the aniline nucleus increases the acidity of the parent ligand almost to the same extent as can be viewed from the magnitude of $\log pK^H$ values. These substituents of *meta*-position transmit electronic charge to nitrogen and hence

its electronegativity increases which results in change of acidity.

The substituted salicylanils are stabilised to a greater extent than the unsubstituted salicylanils. The order of stability runs systematically as

2'-methylsalicylanil < 3'-methylsalicylanil < 4'-methylsalicylanil and 2'-chlorosalicylanil < 3'-chlorosalicylanil < 4'-chloro salicylanil.

Further in compound nos. 9 to 12 the influence of the substituent at the double bonded carbon atom in destabilizing the phenate ion is represented by the order $H < C_2H_5 < CH_3$, the value of the reagent where only H is present as a substituent being taken from literature. In these compounds it appears that probably the inductive effect of the CH_3 and C_2H_5 groups is transmitted by the double bond in benzene to the phenolic oxygen atom thus preventing the ionisation of proton from OH and thereby preventing the formation of hydrogen bond either with ketonic oxygen or nitrogen atom as the case may be. The magnitude of $\log pK^H$ of ligand no. 12 and that of the parent ligand are almost the same. This may perhaps be attributed to the combined effect of C_2H_5 and the substituent OH in the aniline. The constant for compound no. 13 is 10.54 which is higher than the constant of parent ligand by 0.5 log units. The substituent OH in this compound is in the *meta*- position to phenolic OH. This substituent being electrophilic should decrease the electronic charge around the phenolic group and thus should cause an increase in the acid strength of the reagent. The observed value is however contrary to the expectation. The authors feel that in this case the mutual inductive effects of the OH substituents in the same benzene ring in position *meta*- with respect to each other, are acting in opposition. Besides the inductive effect, OH in aniline causes a decrease in the

electronic charge around nitrogen thus weakening the N-H bond. This may be responsible for the poor dissociation of this compound. The combined effect of these substituents may be preventing the dissociation of phenolic OH.

Proton affinity of nitrogen : The values of $\bar{n}_A > 1$ observed for all compounds studied are attributed to the presence of protonated nitrogen in the ligand. It is observed that the magnitude of proton affinity by nitrogen are almost of the same order, and that the proton affinity values of the 2'-hydroxyacetophenone salicylanil and 2'-hydroxypropiofenone salicylanil are higher than the corresponding anils. Earlier in discussion on $\log pK^H$, it was assumed that the mesomeric effect of OH in aniline was responsible for the increased strength of N-H bond. This argument is now substantiated by the observed higher values of N-proton affinity constants of the substituted 2'-hydroxysalicylanils.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
2. L. SACCONI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 126.
3. S. YAMADA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 415.
4. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 83.
5. L. SCHISCHKOFF, *Ann. Chemie*, 1957, 104, 373.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
8. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
9. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
10. K. E. JABALPURWALA, B. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1011.
11. W. B. PERSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 167.
12. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
13. J. H. HEARSON and J. B. GIBERT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2594.